

An assessment of physical strain experienced by manual workers in brick laying operation - A case study in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Despite rapid technological developments, heavy dynamic muscular work and manual material handling will continue to be required for execution of tasks associated with various occupations. This study examined the physical strain experienced by brick layers and the applicability of heart rate indices for measuring physical strain in brick laying operations in south-western region of Nigeria with focus on the maximum energy expenditure and physiological workload during work. It further examined the effect on the workers' productivity. The heart rate of ten brick layers were recorded continuously throughout the working day and applied to heart rate indices. The average working heart rate was 122.8 bt. Min⁻¹, while the pre-work resting heart was 70.5 bt. Min⁻¹. The average physical workload (%HRR) rate was 47.26, while the ratio of working heart rate to resting heart rate was 1.74. The average ratio of working heart rate to 50% level was 0.98. The workers had a mean estimated maximum aerobic capacity (Vo₂max) of 47.77 ml kg⁻¹ min⁻¹. The results showed that an average bricklayer expended high energy which classified brick laying work as heavy work. The energy expenditure was estimated to be 9 Kcal. Min⁻¹, work bout (Tw) and maximum work bout (Tmax) were estimated to be 5.5 minutes and 6.3 minutes respectively. Rest period (R) = 6.2 minutes. This study shows that heart rate indices can be used as an effective means of determining the physiological strain of subjects in applied field situations. There is need to redesign the work content of the aforementioned occupation in order to prevent excessive strain on the workers, which in turn will increase productivity. Manual workers should be tested and evaluated for their physical work capacity for a particular task.

Keywords: Physical Work Load, Brick Laying Worker, Energy Expenditure, Physiological Response, Heart Beat Indices

INTRODUCTION

In a developing country a large percentage of the working population is involved in manual labour where the physical demands of the task often over-tax the physical work capabilities of the worker [25]. For a body to achieve its physical work capacity, series of biochemical processes must take place in form of metabolism

Physical work is performed as a result of muscle action. During aerobic combustion, muscles use oxygen to transform chemical energy in food into mechanical energy. The more energy required carrying out a given task, the more oxygen is needed to necessitate the increased blood circulation. A higher heart rate has been reported to have a close relationship with oxygen consumption, with the rate increasing in proportion to work intensity [1, 8, 12, 30]. Therefore, the physical workload can be estimated by comparing heart rates measured during resting and working.

The part of human body that reveals the physical condition of the most important physiological criteria in the press for oxygen consumption is heart [5]. Oxygen consumption is directly related to the heart beat [5]. These parameters are used to determine metabolic energy consumption [23, 24]. The linear relationship between oxygen consumption and work intensity is an important indicator that heart beats faster when working than resting which is also associated with contraction ratio [6, 32].

While employing manual workers without considering the workers capacity and energy requirement of the tasks, safety of workers is at stake. This could lead to redundancy of the work force and high cost of labour etc

Ergonomist aims to improve efficiency of man at work. The focus of ergonomic investigation is therefore on the interaction between the "man and machine/tasks" [9]. When there is incompatibility between the two aforementioned components, within the work environment, it always results in the worker

experiencing physical or mental strain, with poor performance and lower productivity.

According to Bot and Hollander [4], Haskell et al. [10], Mc Ardle et al. [21] the continuous recording of the heart rate is commonly used to estimate the energy expenditure or physical strain during sports, work or daily activities. This indirect method is based on a linear relationship between the heart rate (HR) and oxygen uptake ($\dot{V}O_2$) during steady state conditions, and gives the opportunity of an easy, non-invasive and relatively inexpensive determination of the $\dot{V}O_2$.

Astrand and Rodahl [2] stated that the work rate is dependent on the subject's body weight in treadmill exercise and on cycle ergometry. The energy output per kilogram and km/hr is more variable in treadmill exercise as it changes with the speed of walking and running, than it is at given workload during cycle ergometer. The energy output on the bicycle ergometer is dependent on the body weight, therefore usage of both treadmill and bicycle ergometer is essential to study the influence of body weight on energy output and work performance.

Venkata et al. [29], revealed higher oxygen consumption (16.9%) and work output (1.3 folds) on treadmill than on bicycle ergometer, as the subjects body weight influences the work rate. This was in tune with the observation of Venkata et al. [28]. All the effort mentioned above are pure laboratory work. However, the sensitivity of this system together with their prohibitive cost, make them difficult to use in field assessment where manual laborers' may be working under hazardous conditions.

The purpose of this paper is to examine the physical strain experience by brick layers and the applicability of heart rate indices for measuring physical strain in brick laying operations in south-western region of Nigeria with focus on the maximum energy expenditure and physiological workload during work. Also to further examine the effect on the workers' productivity during loading, offloading and laying activities.

Materials and Methods

Figure 1. Location of research site Acceptable physical workload

Determination of an acceptable physical workload for heavy dynamic muscular work is based on energy expenditure i.e oxygen consumption ($\dot{V}O_2$). $\dot{V}O_2$ can be measured at work sites with portable devices or estimated by measuring heart rate (HR) [27].

The current acceptable limit for the relative aerobic strain is believed to be lower than 50% of the maximal $\dot{V}O_2$ for bicycling.

Study Location

The research location situated at Ado –Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria is entirely within the tropics. It is located between Longitudes 40 5' and 50 45' East of the Greenwich Meridian and Latitude 70 15' and 80 5' North of the Equator. It lies South of Kwara and Kogi State, East of Osun State and bounded by Ondo-State in the East and South. The location is mainly an upland zone rising over 250 meters above sea level. It has a rhythmically undulating surface. The land scape consists of ancient plains broken by steep-side out cropping dome rocks. These rocks may occur singularly or in groups or ridges. The location enjoys a tropical climate with two distinct seasons. These are the rainy season (April- October) and the dry season (November-March). The temperature ranges between 210 and 280 with total rain fall in the area of 450mm, giving a mean monthly rainfall of 121mm. The average daily relative humidity is 69%.

Field Experiments

Measurements and observation were done for the construction operation (loading- offloading and laying) at the Engineering Building construction site of Afe Babalola University in Ado-Ekiti, Nigeria in summer months, when there was effective construction.

The subjects of the study were ten brick layers working on loading-offloading and laying operations. A working day consists of 8 hours from 08:00 to 17:00, with one hour rest break at 12:00 to 13:00.

The HR of each worker was measured before and during work using automatic sphygmomanometer (Polygon YS796). Weights of the workers were recorded with weighing machine (Harson H89DK) before the commencement of the work. Tape rule was used to measure the height of the workers. $\dot{V}O_2$ of each subject was determined from the HR values obtained during the experiment. $\dot{V}O_{2max}$ was also determined by using Astrand-Astrand nomogram. Thus energy expenditure in brick layering operation was established.

Generally 30-40% levels are recommended for 8hrs work shifts based on habitual work rest. It is generally recommended that for extended work shifts energy cost should not exceed 5Kcal [3], and in form of heart rate measurement, it should not exceed 110 beats per min [18] and Ayoub and Mital [3]. Individual oxygen consumption plays major role in determining physical work

capacity. There are various analogies involved in terms of V as regards to work physiology. They are aerobic power, voluntary oxygen consumption, and cardio-respiratory aerobic capacity. Cardio-respiratory fitness, functional aerobic capacity, energy expenditure etc[10].

Evaluation of physiological workload and energy expenditure were measured from the heart beat values as classified according to Table 3 [15, 22, 31].

Heart Rate

Heart rate is directly related to energy expenditure, as well as oxygen consumption. Therefore heart rate can be used to estimate oxygen consumption, which in turn can be converted into energy expenditure [3, 13, 20, 25, 26]. Energy expenditure (EE) is the amount of work done by a body in kilocalories per minute [11].

Estimated energy output for an adult male in USA is approximately 2500Kcal/day which is approximately 5Kcal/min. recommended maintainable daily work output is 4Kcal/min [11, 21].

Physiological workload or Relative heart rate at work (% HRR) was determined by applying the formula by [31]

$$\% HRR = \frac{HR_w - HR_r}{HR_{max} - HR_r} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

Where, HR_w is the average working heart rate, HR_r is the resting heart rate, HR_{max} is the maximum heart rate that was estimated by using the standard formula of $HR_{max} = 220 - (\text{age})$. 50% level of heart reserve was determined using the formula by [17]

$$50\% \text{ Level} = HR_r + \frac{HR_{max} - HR_r}{2} \quad (2)$$

The ratio of HR_w to HR_r was obtained using the formula by [7]

$$\text{Ratio} = \frac{HR_w}{HR_r} \quad (3)$$

$$BMI = \frac{\text{Weight}(w)}{\text{Height} \times \text{Height}(h^2)} \quad (4)$$

Techniques of Measuring Oxygen Uptake (VO_2)

Louhevaara et al [19] stated that VO_2 can be measured with relative ease in the field with portable devices such as Douglas bags, ox log etc. or can be estimated from HR recordings at the work place. Kolawole and Kehinde [16] used relative aerobic strain (RAS) from Karnoven formula, Kamon and Ayoub [14] had used the linear relationship between HR and VO_2 to predict VO_{2max} . Scott and Christie [25] stated that if expertise equipment not available, using regression equation ($Y=0.259X - 6.422$, where Y= predicted oxygen consumption in $ml.kg^{-1}.min^{-1}$, X = measured heart rate in $beats.min^{-1}$) to predict VO_2 from HR is quite acceptable means for estimating the energy expenditure of manual laborers'.

Due to non-availability of oxygen measuring equipment, this work explored the Scott and Christie [25] regression equation and Astrand-Astrand nomogram to determine the energy expenditure,

physiological response and aerobic strain of brick layering worker including margin of safety on field.

Determining Maximal Oxygen Uptake

Astrand-Astrand nomogram is an age- correction factor used to determine VO_{2max} . Tayyari and Smith [27] give general modified form of the model equation as:

For men:

$$VO_{2max} = AG. (131.5. VO_2) \div (HR-62) \quad (5)$$

For women:

$$VO_{2max} = AG. (131.5. VO_2) \div (HR-72) \quad (6)$$

Where

$$AG = 1.12 - 0.0073 \text{ age.} \quad (7)$$

Production Measurements

Continuous time study was undertaken to determine the percentage of working hour spent on each task. The volume of bricks laid per hour in a day by each worker was derived by multiplying the number of bricks set by the average step volume in cubic meters (m^3).

Workplace, work conditions and work process change regularly in brick laying processes and study forms were prepared according to these changes. The time periods for every course were calculated as 1/100 min, while the amount of time done was determined as number and m^3 . Other factors affecting the study (size of the bricks, distance covered, ground slope and land roughness) were also recorded. There was no interference with workers starting or finishing time, breaks and dealing with other things.

Fatigue

Fatigue is operationally defined as a reduced muscular ability to continue an existing effort. If the energetic work demands exceed about half the person's maximum oxygen uptake, anaerobic energy-yielding metabolic process play increasing roles. This is due to the accumulations of potassium and lactic acid which force the muscle to stop working [16]. The resulting fatigue can be counteracted by the insertion of rest periods.

Rest Periods

Many heavy work activities exceed 5Kcal/min. so rest is needed to compensate. Hedge [11] stated that rest time can be calculated from

$$R = T \frac{(K - S)}{(K - 1.5)} \quad (8)$$

Where R = rest required (min.)

T = total working time (min.)

K = energy required for work (Kcal/min.)

S = desirable standard energy expenditure (Kcal/min.)

1.5 = basal metabolism (Kcal/min.)

The optimal arrangement of work rest cycles

Tayyari and Smith [27] stated that

$$T_{max} = \frac{25}{K - 5} \quad (9)$$

T_{max} = maximum work-bout duration (in minute; beyond which

the work should stop to prevent the development of excessive fatigue. Thus, the work-bout duration (T_w) should be

$$T_w \leq T_{max} \quad (10)$$

The rest duration required for complete restoration of the energy reserve is determined as follows:

$$R = T_w \frac{(K-5)}{5-1.5} = T_w \frac{(K-5)}{3.5} \quad (11)$$

T_w can be determined by an expert job designer having considered workers safety

Results and Discussion

The physical characteristics of each subject are shown in Table 1. The workers had a mean age of 38.5 years (range: 29-46), height of 1.78 m (range: 1.67-1.90) and weight of 76.8Kg (range: 68-83). Their mean body mass index of 24.32 (range: 21.6-26.20)

revealed that they were the correct weight for their height. The workers had a mean estimated maximum aerobic capacity (VO_{2max}) of 47.77 milliliters per kilogram for every minute (range: 42.73-59.36).

Table 1. Physical Characteristics of the Subject

Subject	Mean	Range
Age (years)	38.50	29-46
Weight (Kg)	76.80	68-83
Height (m)	1.78	1.67-1.90
Body Mass Index (BMI)	24.32	21.6-26.20
Resting Heart Rate (Beat/Min)	70.50	65-76
Working Heart Rate (Beat/Min)	122.80	110-132
Estimated VO_2 (ml/Kg/min)	25.68	22.07-28.18
Estimated VO_{2max} (ml/Kg/min)	47.77	42.73-59.36
Percentage Heart Rate Range (%)	47.26	33.61-55.96

Table 2. Mean Heart Rate Indices

Subject	Age	Height	BMI	VO_{2max}	HRw	HRr	%HRR	$\frac{HR_w}{HR_r}$	50% Level	$\frac{HR_w}{50\%level}$
1	42	1.90	21.60	59.36	124	70	50.00	1.77	124	1.00
2	29	1.76	22.00	54.92	110	69	33.61	1.59	130	0.85
3	30	1.85	23.40	47.48	130	72	49.15	1.81	131	0.99
4	34	1.80	23.15	47.22	125	76	44.55	1.64	131	0.95
5	40	1.72	26.02	43.20	132	71	55.96	1.86	126	1.05
6	35	1.83	23.59	47.71	122	67	46.61	1.82	126	0.97
7	38	1.67	25.10	45.12	127	72	50.00	1.76	127	1.00
8	46	1.73	25.39	42.73	124	70	51.92	1.77	122	1.02
9	46	1.75	26.78	44.45	118	65	48.62	1.82	120	0.98
10	45	1.78	26.20	45.52	116	73	42.16	1.59	124	0.94
Mean	38.50	1.78	24.32	47.77	122.80	70.50	47.26	1.74	126.1	0.98
Range	29-46	1.67-1.90	21.60-26.20	42.73-59.36	110-132	65-76	33.61-55.96	1.59-1.86	120-131	0.85-1.05

Evaluation of Physiological Workload and Energy Expenditure

Table 2 shows heart rate indices. The average working heart rates range from 110-132 bt. Min-1 with the overall average working heart rate (HRw) being 122.8 bt. Min-1. The pre-work resting heart rates (HRr) ranged from 65-76 bt. Min-1 with an overall average of 70.5 bt. Min-1. The average physical workload (%HRR) rate was 47.26, while the ratio of working heart rate to resting heart rate was (HRw/HRr) 1.74. The average ratio of working heart rate to 50% level (HRw/50% level) was 0.98. The 50% level and HRw/50% level indices support the %HRR findings. Lammert [17] suggested that 50% level can be successfully used as a simple and elective way of measuring strain. Lammert [17] stated that if the ratio of heart rate at work to 50% level is equal to 1, then the work being undertaken can be classified as hard continuous work.

Since the average value of % HHR is 47.26%, the physiological workload is evaluated as 47% in terms of weight of moulded brick which is classified as heavy work in its class (40-50 groups). Heavy work on the features of the group (7.5-10 Kcal per minute

energy expenditure), and the heart beat rate between 110-132 beat/min. (Table 3).

Table 3. Grades of Physical Work

Grade of Work	Energy expenditure (Kcal/min)	Energy expenditure (Kcal/day)	Heart Rate (beat/min)	Physiological Workload (%)
Resting	1.5	<720	50-60	0-10
Very light work	1.6-2.5	768-1200	60-70	10-20
Light work	2.5-5.0	1200-2400	70-90	20-30
Moderate work	5.0-7.5	2400-3600	90-110	30-40
Heavy work	7.5-10	3600-4800	110-130	40-50
Very heavy work	10.0-12.5	4800-6000	130-150	50-60
Unduly heavy work	>12.5	>6000	>150	>60

Production Measurement Evaluation

Average hourly production decreases by 10 bricks per hour in the afternoon from the work study prepared. This was noticed to be caused by fatigue when maximum work-bout (Tmax) was exceeded, and there was accumulation of potassium and lactic acid which forces the muscle to stop working [16], therefore rest period was incorporated. As stated by Scott and Christie [25] and others in the literature, heart rate is directly related to energy expenditure. From the result of heart rate indices, physiological workload (MEAN %HRR = 47.26). It can be assumed that 9 Kilocalories of energy is used per minute. This required 6.3 minutes for the maximum work-bout (Tmax), having work-bout duration (Tw) assumed to be 5.5 minutes by considering some factors of safety and 6.2 minutes as the required rest for recovery.

CONCLUSIONS

The heart beat indices reveal that the average work heart beat is 122.8 bt. min⁻¹. The average physical work load (%HRR) is 47.26 %. The workers had a mean estimated maximum aerobic capacity (V02max) of 47.77 ml. Kg⁻¹ Min⁻¹. According to all these physiological measurement, an average brick layer during the operation will experience physiological aerobic strain.

With the energy expenditure estimated to be 9 Kcal. Min⁻¹, maximum work-bout (Tmax) of 6.3 minutes, work-bout (Tw) assumed to be 5.5 minutes and rest (R) to be 6.2 minutes, the task of brick laying is regarded as heavy work.

The estimated values of physiological workload and energy expenditure have the tendency to affect the productivity and performance of the workers.

Recommendations

There is need to redesign the work content of the aforementioned occupation in order to prevent excessive strain on the workers, which in turn will increase productivity.

Workers undertaking bricklaying operations should have some rest, observed frequent short pauses to achieve an optimum work rate.

Likewise, providing a good working environment that includes protective safety tools will greatly improve productivity.

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